

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 2-(6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-halophenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide

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Abstract : A number of new 2-(6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-halophenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide (5a-o) have been synthesized and screened for antibacterial activity.

Keywords : Benzothiazole, synthesis, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Compounds having benzothiazole moiety possess diverse pharmacological activities viz. antibacterial^{1,2}, anticonvulsant³, antitumour⁴, antiinflammatory⁵, antitubercular⁶, etc. In this study a series of 2-(6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-halophenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide (5a-o) have been prepared by refluxing equimolar quantity of 2-hydrazino-6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazole (3a-e) and 4-substituted phenylisothiocyanate (4a-c). 2-Hydrazino-6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazole (3a-e) have been synthesized by refluxing of 6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-amine (2a-e) with hydrazine hydrate in presence of conc. hydrochloric acid and ethylene glycol. 4-Substituted phenylisothiocyanate (4a-c) were prepared by reaction of 4-substituted aromatic amines with carbon disulfide in presence of ammonia⁷. 2-(6-Substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-halophenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide (5a-o) yielded according to the Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

A series of 2-(6-substituted-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-halophenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide (5a-o) was synthesized and their structures was elucidated by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectra. Yields, melting points, R_f values, calculated log P values and mol. formulas in Table 2.

Antimicrobial activity :

The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* (Gram negative) and *S. aureus* (Gram positive) by cup-plate methods⁸. All the observations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Antibacterial screening results of compounds 5a-o

Compd.	Antibacterial activity			
	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	
	50 (mcg/ml)	100 (mcg/ml)	50 (mcg/ml)	100 (mcg/ml)
5a	++	+++	++	+++
5b	+	++	++	+++
5c	+	++	+	++
5d	++	+++	+	++
5e	++	++	++	+++
5f	+	++	++	+++
5g	+	++	+	++
5h	++	++	++	+++
5i	++	+++	++	++
5j	++	++	++	+++
5k	++	+++	++	+++
5l	+	++	++	+++
5m	++	+++	+	++
5n	++	+++	++	+++
5o	+	++	++	++
Sterptomycin (Std)	+++	++++	+++	++++

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.
(10–15 mm) = + Active, (15–18 mm) = ++ mildly active, (18–20 mm) = +++ moderately active, (21 mm, up) = ++++ highly active.

Table 2. Physical data of compounds 5a-o

Compd.	R	R ¹	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	R _f ^a	Calcd. log P ^b value	Mol. formula
5a	Cl	F	126	96	0.32	4.88 ± 0.66	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClFN ₄ S ₂
5b	Br	F	140	94	0.36	5.06 ± 0.68	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrFN ₄ S ₂
5c	F	F	142	92	0.32	4.34 ± 0.68	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ F ₂ N ₄ S ₂
5d	CH ₃	F	133	95	0.38	4.75 ± 0.65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₄ S ₂
5e	OCH ₃	F	141	90	0.33	4.20 ± 0.92	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₄ OS ₂
5f	Cl	Br	135	95	0.30	5.60 ± 0.66	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ S ₂
5g	Br	Br	138	94	0.34	5.78 ± 0.68	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₄ S ₂
5h	F	Br	135	92	0.34	5.06 ± 0.68	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrFN ₄ S ₂
5i	CH ₃	Br	130	96	0.36	5.47 ± 0.65	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ S ₂
5j	OCH ₃	Br	137	94	0.35	4.92 ± 0.92	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ BrN ₄ OS ₂
5k	Cl	Cl	132	96	0.30	5.43 ± 0.64	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ S ₂
5l	Br	Cl	139	94	0.35	5.60 ± 0.66	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ BrClN ₄ S ₂
5m	F	Cl	140	93	0.33	4.88 ± 0.66	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ClFN ₄ S ₂
5n	CH ₃	Cl	128	95	0.39	5.29 ± 0.63	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ S ₂
5o	OCH ₃	Cl	139	93	0.34	4.75 ± 0.89	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ OS ₂

^aBenzene (9) : ethanol (1), ^bcalculated by ACD/ChemSketch Freeware.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries in liquid paraffin and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Shimadzu IR 200 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra recorded Bruker Avance II 400

spectrometer. Mass spectra recorded on a Jeol mass spectrophotometer at 70 eV.

6-Chloro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-amine (2a) : To glacial acetic acid (150 ml) precooled to 5 °C, potassium

thiocyanate (0.06 mol) and 4-chloroaniline (0.06 mol) (**1a**) were added. The mixture was placed in freezing mixture and stirred mechanically with addition of bromine (0.02 mol in 10 ml glacial acetic acid) from a dropping funnel at such a rate that temperature does not rise above 5 °C. After all the bromine has been added (105 min), the solution was stirred for an additional 2 h at 0–10 °C. The residue was collected by filtration and dissolved in hot water (150 ml). The solution was filtered and filtrate was neutralized with conc. ammonia solution to pH 6. The precipitate of **2a** resulted was collected and crystallized from ethanol, yield : 78%; m.p. 170 °C; ν_{\max} 3425 (1° NH), 1530 (aromatic C=C), 1632 (C=N), 1442 (thiazole), 1320 (C–N), 716 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ (DMSO) 6.8 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.1–7.5 (3H, m, Ar-H). The other compounds of the series were prepared by similar procedure (yield : 67–75%) : **2b**, m.p. 172 °C; **c**, 169 °C; **d**, 162 °C; **e**, 164 °C.

2-Hydrazino-6-chloro-1,3-benzothiazole (3a) : Conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to hydrazine hydrate (10.0 g, 0.2 mol) at 5–10 °C followed by ethylene glycol (40 ml). Thereafter, 6-chloro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-amine (0.01 mol) (**2a**) was added in portions and the resultant mixture was refluxed for 2 h and then cooled. The fine crystalline solid separated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallization from ethanol, yield : 72%; m.p. 198 °C; ν_{\max} 3425 (1° NH), 3200 (2° NH), 1530 (aromatic C=C), 1632 (C=N), 1442 (thiazole), 1320 (C–N), 716 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ (DMSO) 4.8 (2H, s, NH_2), 8.9 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–7.5 (3H, m, Ar-H). The other compounds of the series were prepared by similar procedure (yield : 60–70%) : **3b**, m.p. 200 °C; **c**, 204 °C; **d**, 198 °C; **e**, 193 °C.

2-(6-Chloro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-N-(4-fluorophenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide (5a) : A equimolar mixture of 2-hydrazino-6-chloro-1,3-benzothiazole (**3a**) and 4-fluorophenylisothiocyanate (**4a**) in benzene (50 ml) was

refluxed for 3–6 h. A white product gradually separated out. It was filtered hot, dried and crystallized from methanol, yield : 96% ; m.p. 126 °C; ν_{\max} 3200 (2° NH), 1530 (aromatic C=C), 1632 (C=N), 1442 (thiazole), 1320 (C–N), 1220 (C=S), 1100 (aromatic F), 716 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ (DMSO) 9.3 (1H, s, NH), 9.8 (1H, s, NH), 10.1 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–7.7 (7H, m, Ar-H); m/z 352 (M^+) (Found : C, 51.71; H, 5.03; N, 18.05. Calcd. C, 51.80; H, 5.15; N, 18.27%). The other compounds of the series were prepared by similar procedure (yield : 90–96%) : **5b**, m.p. 140 °C; **c**, 142 °C; **d**, 133 °C; **e**, 141 °C; **f**, 135 °C; **g**, 138 °C; **h**, 135 °C; **i**, 130 °C; **j**, 137 °C; **k**, 132 °C; **l**, 139 °C; **m**, 140 °C; **n**, 128 °C; **o**, 139 °C.

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